

SURVEY QUESTIONS

TABLE 1: Survey Questions

#	Question	Answer choices
Section 1: Demographics		
Q1	Do you participate in ...?	[Slack, Gitter, both, none, other]
Q2	What is your gender?	[female, male, other]
Q3	What is the highest computer science degree you have completed?	[student, college diploma, bachelor's degree, master's degree, professional degree, doctorate, self-taught, other]
Q4	What is your current employment status?	[employed full time, employed part time, unemployed, student, self-employee, retired, other]
Q5	What is your overall software development experience?	[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10+] years
Q13	What is your role in the project or the technology associated to the chatroom team?	[user, maintainer, contributor, no active role, other]
Section 2: Motivations		
Q6	What are your motivations for asking questions on the chatrom?	open-ended question
Q7	Can you tell us about specific cases when the chatroom helped you to solve issues?	open-ended question
Q8	What are your motivations for answering questions on the chatroom?	open-ended question
Q9	Can you tell us about specific cases when you helped to solve issues on the chatroom?	open-ended question
Q10	What types of issues/topics do you mostly discuss on the chatroom?	open-ended question
Q11	When would you use the chatroom rather than other developer platforms?	open-ended question
Section 3: Impacts		
Q12	What is the chatroom team you are most active in? (you can answer the following questions with the selected team in mind)	open-ended question
Q14	If it applies, do you think that the chatroom has an impact on the quality of the associated project or technology? How?	open-ended question
Q15	Do you also think that the chatroom has an impact on the quality of your own projects? How?	open-ended question
Q16	Do you think that the chatroom has an impact on your productivity? How?	open-ended question
Q17	Do you think that the chatroom has an impact on the retention of developers that use the project or the technology?	open-ended question
Q18	If it applies, do you think that the chatroom has an impact on the resolution time of issues in the associated project or technology? How?	open-ended question
Section 4: Quality determinants		
Q19	In your opinion, what makes a good chatroom?	open-ended question
Q20	In your opinion, how can the chatroom be improved?	open-ended question
Q21	Overall, how would you rate your experience using the chatroom?	[1, 2, 3, 4, 5] (1 being poor to 5 being excellent)